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From colonisation to causation: the links between Group B Streptococcus colonisation, invasive disease, and preterm birth

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Abstract

Advances in the development of vaccines against Group B Streptococcus (GBS) may soon offer an alternative approach to preventing neonatal GBS infections. However, children who are born preterm may not receive full protection from such vaccines, either because they are born before vaccine delivery, or because of less effective maternal antibodies transfer. With this as our motivation, we discuss causal links between maternal GBS colonisation, invasive GBS disease, and preterm birth, together with supporting evidence. Whilst multiple studies indicate that maternal colonisation can cause both disease and preterm birth, we argue that direct causal links between preterm birth and invasive disease require further clarification, in particular with regard to *in utero* onset versus postnatal early-onset disease. Further, recent findings on the role of prematurity as effect modifier of GBS-related outcomes are examined. We discuss implications of these causal links and questions that should be addressed to guide studies and policy.

Keywords: Group B Streptococcus, preterm birth, neonatal infections, causal inference, confounding, effect modification

Manuscript

Background

Globally, ~92,000 infants were estimated to have died in 2020 following severe infections caused by the Group B Streptococcus (GBS) bacterium (1). The progress in the development of maternal vaccines that prevent neonatal GBS disease to address this burden has prompted interest in understanding determinants of GBS infection incidence and long-term outcomes so that the future vaccine impact can be estimated. In this context, one important aspect of the epidemiology of GBS infection during early life relates to the intricate relations between maternal colonisation by GBS, invasive neonatal GBS disease (iGBSd), and preterm birth, which itself can lead to considerable morbidity and mortality . For example, maternal GBS colonisation not only is the main risk factor for iGBSd during the first week of life (early-onset iGBSd), but is also associated with an increased risk of preterm birth. Prematurity, in its turn, is a risk factor for iGBSd, as well as for increased severity of acute presentation (acute mortality) and long-term sequelae caused by this infection.

Here, we discuss different causal links between GBS colonisation of mothers, iGBSd and preterm birth, how they might impact children's health and which questions remain unanswered and could be prioritised in future epidemiologic research. **Figure 1** presents a series of diagrams that show the causal relationships which we discuss in the following sections.

Figure 1. Directed acyclic graphs (2) representing potential causal relations described in the different sections of this manuscript. Variables C, P, D, and M correspond, respectively, to GBS colonisation, preterm birth, GBS disease, and early-life mortality. Although these diagrams are simplifications of the underlying causal structure (e.g. common causes of P and M or of C and P [see for example section Epidemiology of GBS vaginal colonization in (3) for a discussion of factors associated with maternal GBS colonization] might exist that would need to be included), they have some clear implications: there is a non-causal path $D \leftarrow C \rightarrow P$ that might bias analyses on preterm birth and GBS disease; the relation between GBS disease and early-life mortality would also be biased if the non-causal path $M \leftarrow P \rightarrow D$ is not accounted for (we assume that there are no directed paths from maternal GBS colonisation to early-life mortality that do not include GBS disease and prematurity). Note that for late-onset cases, studies (4) provide evidence that the effect of prenatal maternal GBS colonisation (C) on D could be partially mediated by persistence of colonisation during the postnatal period; that is, $C \rightarrow \text{“Postnatal C”} \rightarrow D$. These panels are discussed further in the main text: *Panel I* is discussed in the section “Maternal GBS colonisation: a risk factor for both invasive GBS disease and preterm birth”; *Panels II and III*, in the section “Preterm birth and the risk of invasive GBS disease”; and *Panel IV*, in “GBS-related acute and long-term outcomes in term and preterm children”.

Panel I

Panel II

Panel III

Panel IV

Maternal GBS colonisation: a risk factor for both invasive GBS disease and preterm birth
(Figure 1, Panel I)

That GBS colonisation of the maternal genito-urinary tract is responsible for most early-onset iGBSd cases is uncontroversial, with exposure to the pathogen occurring either *in utero* or during delivery. In addition to experimental, mechanistic studies (3, 5-7), observational evidence includes studies that compared colonisation status of mothers of early-onset iGBSd patients to mothers of healthy newborns (8), and the reductions in incidence (9) of early-onset disease observed after policy implementation of intrapartum antibiotics for pregnant women colonised before delivery. Further, a link between GBS bacterial load and early-onset iGBSd has also been reported (8, 10).

In contrast, the contribution of maternal colonisation to late-onset (from 7 to 90 days of life) iGBSd is less clear. Several epidemiologic studies have reported an association between prenatal maternal colonisation and late-onset iGBSd (11); however, postnatal colonisation (possibly also from the mother to her newborn) might also lead to late-onset disease (12). For example, a French longitudinal study showed frequent *de novo* colonisation of infants by the hypervirulent clone CC17 in the first months of life (13). Moreover, there is evidence that some late-onset cases are due to nosocomial transmission (14). Quantification of the fractions of late-onset cases attributable to these different mechanisms, including to perinatal and postnatal mother-to-neonate GBS transmission, would thus provide valuable information for policy making and prioritisation of research on and development of prevention strategies.

In addition to its direct role in the pathogenesis of iGBSd, colonisation of the maternal genito-urinary tract by GBS has been associated with preterm birth. The causal nature of this link has

been supported by evidence from non-human experimental studies (15, 16), and might involve ascending infection of foetal membranes (17, 18), with associated tissue damage and inflammatory response that could promote uterine contractility. However, despite the mechanistic evidence, there is uncertainty about the extent to which GBS colonisation increases risk of preterm birth and previous systematic reviews (17, 19) showed considerable heterogeneity in the magnitude of associations reported in individual studies. A recent simulation study (20) suggests that the time-varying nature of GBS colonisation could contribute to the heterogeneity in such results. In particular, this simulation study showed that assessments of colonisation during early pregnancy mean that for a non-negligible fraction of study participants GBS colonisation status would have changed by the time when most preterm births occur, either because of GBS bacteria clearance or acquisition. Consistent with this, longitudinal studies (21, 22) that used repeated microbiological assessments showed that not all pregnant women found to be colonised in the first or second trimester of gestation remain colonised with GBS during the third trimester; women might also become colonised only in the final weeks of gestation. Some of the observed heterogeneity in results might also be linked to unmeasured confounders present in different populations. Longitudinal studies, ideally starting follow-up in the second trimester, with repeated rectovaginal screening and that use sensitive microbiological methods and test for different GBS serotypes and that record information on gestational age at birth would clarify the relative contributions of study design and pathogen populations to the reported variability in results.

Finally, note that pregnant women with chorioamnionitis due to GBS might also be at increased risk of preterm birth (23); it is likely, in this case, that chorioamnionitis is a mediator of the effect of GBS colonisation on preterm birth risk.

Preterm birth and the risk of invasive GBS disease (Figure 1, Panels II and III)

Researchers have long been interested in studying a direct causal relation between preterm birth and iGBSd, which would be consistent with an overall increased susceptibility to bacterial infections in preterm babies. Note, however, that as GBS colonisation of mothers might represent a common cause of both iGBSd and preterm birth, these two conditions are expected to be associated even if there are no direct causal relations between them (in other words, GBS colonisation is a confounder of their relationship). Both studies that adjust and studies that do not adjust for maternal GBS colonisation suggest an increased risk of early-onset iGBSd among preterm compared to term babies (8, 24, 25). For example, in the study by Benitz and colleagues (8), decreasing gestational age was associated with progressively increasing risk of early-onset GBS disease (see Table 7 in that study).

Analyses restricted to late-onset cases also suggest that preterm infants have a higher risk of disease (9, 11, 26). For example, in a study (12) conducted in Italy, the incidence of late-onset iGBSd was higher in preterm newborns (1.4 cases/1,000 live births) compared to term newborns (0.24 cases/1,000 live births). The mechanisms responsible for this association between late-onset cases and prematurity might include immaturity of the immune system (27), lower transfer of maternal IgG antibodies for babies born earlier in pregnancy (28) and longer periods of hospitalisation that could increase risk of nosocomially-acquired infection (4).

Considerations based on this and the previous section suggest a possible causal structure that represents the relationship between maternal GBS colonisation, GBS disease and preterm birth (**Figure 1, Panel II**). In contrast, *Panel III* of **Figure 1** describes the plausible scenario where iGBSd cases start as an *in utero* invasive infection, and where iGBSd might represent a cause,

rather than an effect, of preterm birth. This would be consistent with a link between GBS colonisation and preterm birth, and for example with the reported association between chorioamnionitis and neonatal sepsis in preterm infants (see for example the systematic review in (29), which is not GBS specific) as well as with an earlier finding that chorioamnionitis was often present in mothers of babies who develop sepsis despite intrapartum antibiotics (see Chorioamnionitis section in (8)). Note that *Panel III* of **Figure 1** would not depict causal processes for all cases, but rather for a fraction thereof, and that its relevance might depend on the degree of heterogeneity in iGBSd pathogenesis. In other words, the causal structure that is pertinent for a particular case will depend on whether iGBSd had *in utero* or postnatal onset. Alternatively, both GBS cases with *in utero* onset and GBS cases with postnatal onset could be represented in the same causal diagram using different variables. Note that one consequence of the presence of infections with *in utero* onset, and of their frequent non-discernibility from early-onset infections with postnatal onset, is that the interpretation of analyses on the effect of prematurity on GBS disease risk might not be straightforward. Finally, it is worth mentioning that although the fraction of early-onset GBS cases that correspond to infections with *in utero* onset has not, to our knowledge, been estimated, a systematic review (30) suggests that most (68%) children with early-onset GBS disease present symptoms on the first day of life, and in a UK-based study performed between 1998 and 2000, 19/37 early-onset cases had symptoms by one hour of life (25). However, data were not reported on whether this percentage is higher in preterm versus term infants, which would support the hypothesis in *Panel III*.

GBS-related acute and long-term outcomes in term and preterm children (Figure 1, Panel IV)

GBS disease and preterm birth are both, in their own right, important causes of acute mortality during the neonatal period (30, 31) and of long-term sequelae among survivors (32, 33). This

relationship is depicted in **Figure 1, Panel IV**. Recently, there has been interest in quantifying the consequences of their co-occurrence. A large cohort study (34) including national data from both Denmark and the Netherlands assessed whether preterm birth modifies the effect of iGBSd on mortality and found that the mortality rate in the 3 months following onset of iGBSd was higher in preterm babies compared to term babies; note however that in Denmark, but not the Netherlands, the death rate was equally high in preterm infants who developed iGBSd versus preterm children with no history of iGBSd. These findings on 3-month mortality are consistent, for example, with results of an American study in which fatality rates for both early- and late-onset cases were higher in preterm infants compared to term infants (9). Further, in the Danish-Dutch study, preterm infants with a history of iGBSd were at considerably higher risk of moderate/severe neurodevelopmental impairment compared to preterm infants who did not develop iGBSd, and to term infants with iGBSd (5.6, 2.4, 2.5%, respectively at the age of 5 in Denmark, and 7.2, 2.0 and 2.2% in the Netherlands). Similar findings were observed in Norway, where, amongst children with iGBSd diagnosis, higher mortality and more frequent long-term impairment were observed in those born preterm (35). Another recent study (36) from Denmark also reported that risk of epilepsy after iGBSd was twice as high in preterm versus term infants. Despite these several recent studies, whether preterm babies are at increased risk of impairment in particular neurodevelopmental domains is less clear, and warrants further research.

Note that for early-onset infections with *in utero* onset, preterm birth is a mediator in the causal path from infection to mortality. For cases with postnatal onset (see previous section), on the other hand, preterm birth might be a confounder of the effect of GBS infection on mortality.

Importance for vaccine impact

Currently, the only public health intervention available to reduce the incidence of iGBSd is the intrapartum administration of antibiotics for women who are colonised with GBS or who present other known risk factors for early-onset GBS disease. Although adoption of this strategy has led to important reductions in the number of cases of early-onset GBS disease, there are limitations with this approach, including that it does not prevent late-onset GBS disease and might increase the risk of antimicrobial resistance. As briefly mentioned in the *Background* section, recently, there have been advances in the clinical development of maternal GBS vaccines (37), which suggest that a more efficient and easily deployable preventive intervention might soon become available. Much of our discussion in the previous sections is relevant to the studies that will quantify the future impact of maternal vaccines against GBS. Here, we highlight two aspects: first, the question on the extent to which GBS colonisation increases risk of preterm birth is crucial because it is conceivable that maternal GBS vaccines might also have an effect on GBS carriage – this would be a benefit of the vaccination that would not be directly related to its impact on invasive disease risk.

A second aspect of the epidemiology of GBS that should be carefully considered when assessing vaccine impact is the role of prematurity on the burden linked to iGBSd. Indeed, preterm babies are at increased risk of both early- and late-onset GBS disease compared to children who are born at term, and when preterm children develop iGBSd they are more likely to die and develop long-term impairments. The related discussion in different sections of the manuscript suggests that stratifying incidence, risk of acute mortality and long-term sequelae by gestational age categories could generate more accurate burden estimates, and improve their transportability to settings with different frequencies of preterm birth. Having burden-related

parameter estimates stratified by gestational age categories would be particularly important if future clinical trials suggest that vaccine effect might vary by gestational age at birth.

Finally, it is also likely that future vaccine trials and effectiveness studies will generate data that will allow a better understanding of the different questions discussed here, for example, by including prospective follow-up of pregnant women and newborns, and recording detailed microbiological and gestational age information.

Future directions

In addition to sharing a common cause, maternal GBS colonisation, preterm birth and iGBSd might also be directly causally linked. For instance, preterm birth might increase the risk of GBS disease, and also be associated with more severe post-GBS sequelae. Although our understanding of the links between these conditions is based on robust epidemiologic evidence, several knowledge gaps persist that, if addressed, would help to better guide GBS risk assessment, public health interventions, including targeted treatment, and design of maternal GBS vaccine studies. In **Table 1**, we suggest possible research questions for future studies and explain why their answers are likely to be impactful. In particular, we believe that further clarification of the role of specific serotypes and sequence types of GBS in the pathogenesis of GBS-related preterm birth, and early- and late-onset iGBSd might help to explain between-study and -geographical region variation in estimates of effect measures on preterm birth, and incidence for GBS disease. This, together with better understanding of the factors discussed in this paper, could lead to more precise estimates of GBS burden, as well as inform optimisation of existing and future prevention strategies.

Table 1. Possible research questions for future studies. Some questions in this table have been the focus of previous studies; however we believe systematic studies with data from more settings are needed. Abbreviations: EOGBS, early-onset invasive GBS disease; LOGBS, late-onset invasive GBS disease.

Link	Future research question	Importance/Relevance
	<p><i>GBS colonisation and GBS disease</i></p> <p>What are the GBS serotype- and sequence type (e.g. sequence type 17)-specific risks of EOGBS given maternal colonisation? And are there other genetic virulence factors associated with higher EOGBS risk?</p> <p>What is the contribution of perinatal and postnatal maternal colonisation to LOGBS incidence? And is it setting-dependent? (Could these questions be addressed by paired longitudinal microbiological testing of mothers and neonates?)</p> <p><i>GBS colonisation and preterm birth</i></p>	<p>Relevant for modelling the impact of maternal GBS vaccines, of more targeted prevention measures for colonisation due to highly virulent GBS subtypes, and to understand differences in EOGBS incidence</p> <p>Possible explanation for differences in LOGBS incidence and clinical presentation</p>

<p>Is the increase in risk of preterm birth associated with particular GBS serotypes?</p> <p>Does density of GBS colonisation influence the risk of preterm birth?</p> <p>Is the association between GBS colonisation and preterm birth partially related to other microbiological/microbiome changes in the maternal genito-urinary tract?</p>	<p>More precise estimation of the increase in risk of preterm birth; possible explanation for heterogeneity of results of observational studies</p> <p>Mechanistic insights, and possible clinical prediction</p> <p>Understand how much preterm birth risk might change if an intervention were developed and deployed to reduce GBS colonisation during pregnancy</p>
<p><i>Preterm birth and GBS disease</i></p>	
<p>What is the proportion of EOGBS cases that represent a likely cause of preterm birth?</p>	<p>Implications for how data should be analysed and interpreted; implications for timing of interventions to reduce EOGBS risk</p>
<p>When, during the neonatal period, is the risk of invasive GBS disease highest for preterm babies?</p>	<p>Guide policy to reduce risk of LOGBS in preterm babies</p>
<p>Can the risk of LOGBS in preterm babies explain some of the geographical differences in LOGBS incidence?</p>	<p>Potential contributing factor for the variation in LOGBS incidence</p>
<p><i>Effect modification of GBS outcomes by preterm status</i></p>	
<p>Are preterm babies at higher risk of GBS-related impairment in particular developmental domains?</p>	<p>Guide clinical follow-up of children born preterm who survive GBS disease</p>

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